

Observable Markov decision processes with stochastic actions applicable on the financial market

Executive summary

The Markov Decision Process is an important mathematical model used to predict the future outcomes of a variety of events. Markov Decision Process is a widely used model which is applied in a plethora of fields. It is used in robotics, finance, automatic control and as well as in economics. A few examples could be seen ranging from automation industries to C.O.B.O.T(collaborative robot). In the paper below a critical analysis of a comprehensive description of how Markov Decision Process is applied in determining the fluctuations of the value of crypto currency has been provided. The paper also explains how The Markov decision process is used in evaluating the future performance of the blockchain system.

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Introduction

In today's world, we are all bound to make decisions pretty much every day. Be it individuals or a company as a whole, we all need to make decisions every single day regarding various aspects of life. There are various probabilities for our decisions to turn out to be bad or good. However, mathematically speaking there is a method by which we can try and formulate decision-making processes (Guo et al., 2018). Markov decision process is said to be a process that involves discrete-time stochastic control. Markov decision process helps us in having two different outcomes of decision-making processes (Airo Web, 2022). One of which involves random outcomes and another one involves an outcome that is controlled by the decision-maker. Dynamic programming is required to find solutions to optimization problems and in the Markov decision process (MDP) we study that. Markov decision process has its origin in the 1950s. The name Markov decision process comes from the Russian scientist named Andrey Markov. Markov decision process is used in various fields which include automatic control, manufacturing, robotics, and economics. The Markov decision process is used in many companies to calculate and formulate decisions so that the company can be successful in the future. It has wide usage and it is an important concept that needs to be understood. The following discussion will provide a detailed and comprehensive description of Markov decision process and why it is important. The paper also discusses about the places where the method can be used. Calculations and images have been used for better understanding of the topic.

Markov Decision Process in Block chain System

In recent years there has been a growing importance of block chains. Therefore, it is important to evaluate and determine the performance of block chains in the future and to find if there is some chance to facilitate improvement. Markov Decision Process is a key mathematical tool using which evaluation of faults in block chain process can be acknowledged (Zheng and Namin 2018). The Markov Decision Process is also used to determine the magnitude of the impact posed by transaction fees on those mining strategies of the bit coin network which are selfish.

Markov Processes

$X(t)$ satisfies the Markov Property (memoryless) which

States that

For any choice of time instants $t_i, i=1, \dots, n$ where $t_j > t_i$

For $j > k$

$$P\{X(t_{n+1})=x_{n+1} | X(t_n)=x_n \dots \dots X(t_1)=x_1\} = P\{X(t_{n+1})=x_{n+1} | X(t_n)=x_n\}$$

Memory less property as the state of the system at future time t_{n+1} is decided by the system state at the current time t_n and does not depend on the state at earlier time instants $t_1, \dots, t_{n-1}$.

Memoryless property is also known as the forgetfulness property. This property states that probability of a given distribution has absolutely nothing to do with its history. It has an independent relationship with its history. No matter what time it is, one can label it as time zero.

Due to the property of independency, in case a probability distribution possesses the memoryless property (forgetfulness property), the possibility of any given event occurring in the future has zero connection to whether or not the same event has previously happened. The past of the function does not effect the future because they are not related.

Markov Decision Process used in Crypto Currency

As crypto currency is not uniform in nature, it is important to predict its value before investing in it. The value of crypto currency is likely to fluctuate with respect to the market conditions. Therefore, a mathematical tool is required to determine the possibility of the value of crypto currency in the future (Tang et al., 2018). Markov Decision Process is highly effective mathematical tools that can almost accurately predict the most likely value of the crypto currency in the future market, thus helping the investors to decide on their investments.

Markov Decision Process in Reinforcement Learning

Markov Decision Process is a key tool that helps in critically analyzing the environment of reinforcement learning. Rewards are values that are received by the agents who are performing a task. These rewards can be both positive and negative and it highly depends on the performance of the agent (Yousefi et al., 2020). As reward keeps fluctuating, to determine the possible reward in reinforcement learning, the Markov Decision Process comes in handy.

Markov Chains and Control Problems

Constraints that are associated with problems have a separate class of Markov Decision Process, where state-resource restrictions are needed to be satisfied by optimal. This type of problem has been thoroughly investigated, primarily for the case of policies related to stationary control. The Lagrangian methodology is the basic approach to the problems that will help in transforming from constraints to unconstrained ones, however, it is possible due to mixed criteria, which involves the linear combination of constrained and minimized functional (Shou et al., 2020). With the help of the Markov Decision Process and using the process of linear programming setting, this problem can be reduced. However, this process is limited to systems of the infinite time interval. The most important concern regarding the dimensional linear programming problem is that the solution of the programming can be processed only in simple cases that can be solved using an analytical process. However, on the other hand, the numerical procedure can be very difficult to be used.

Computational Social Network

Computational Social Network portrays papers which are referred and it deals with various mathematical, computational and all the other aspects that are involved in social computing (Goyal and Grand-Clement 2018). Markov Decision Process plays an important role which facilitates the computational networks as a mathematical model that has a specific algorithm.

Linear control theory and Structured Markov Chains

There has been a detailed study performed on the analysis of stability and controller design of discrete Markov jump. Linear network control system has undergone critical analysis over the years and the primary focus of the study was redirected towards the partially acknowledged transition matrices which attempt to eliminate the prior knowledge of the matrices (Yu et al., 2019). As a category of systems which are partially known as transition probabilities, a design of feedback controller is done and with help of linear matrix inequality, a sufficient condition for stochastic stability of underlying system is performed.

Stochastic Markov Chain

What is a Stochastic Matrix?

$x_0 = \begin{bmatrix} A \\ B \end{bmatrix}$

from: A B to: A B
 $P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 & 0.50 \\ 0.75 & 0.50 \end{bmatrix}$
Add to 1
Stochastic

from: A B to: A B
 $P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 & 0.75 \\ 0.50 & 0.50 \end{bmatrix}$
Add to 1
Stochastic

from: A B to: A B
 $P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.1 \\ 0.2 & 0.8 \end{bmatrix}$
Does not add to 1
Not Stochastic

from: A B to: A B
 $P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.2 \\ 0.3 & 0.9 \end{bmatrix}$
Does not add to 1
Not Stochastic

A Markov Chain is a stochastic model which was created by Andrey Markov. This Markov chain provides an outline of possibilities arranged in a chronology of events happening based on the nature of the past event (Bi et al., 2019). The Markov Chain is a very common and frequently used

model that is applied in various industries and it deals with sequential data, like finance. The Page rank algorithm is a type of Markov Chain. This algorithm is used to the famous search engine Google, and it helps Google to identify the sequence in which links are to be displayed. With the help of mathematics, this Markov chain can help is in predicting the future with the best possible accuracy (Roy, Chowdhury and Aslam 2018). The primary goal of the Markov method is to evaluate the possibility of changing from one state to another. One of the most significant use of Markov is to identify the stochastic variable whose possible future state depends on its past. Unofficially, stochastic variable can be defined as a variable with values depending on the results of random happenings of events.

Stochastic Matrix

To every stochastic matrix $P = (p_{ij})$, $i, j = 0, 1, \dots$ there exists a homogeneous Markov chain $\{X_n, n = 0, 1, \dots\}$ with state space $S = \{0, 1, \dots\}$ and one-step transition probability p_{ij} , $i, j \in S$.

That is, to every stochastic matrix P , there corresponds a Markov chain $\{X_n\}$ for which P is the unit-step transition matrix. Then $P^2 = (p_{ij}^{(2)})$ is also stochastic; it is the two-step transition matrix for the chain $\{X_n, n = 0, 1, \dots\}$. However, not every stochastic matrix is the two-step transition matrix of a Markov chain.

Stochastic Process $X(t)$

Process takes on random values, $X(t_1)=x_1, \dots, X(t_n)=x_n$. At times $t_1, \dots, t_n$

The random variables $x_1, \dots, x_n, \dots$ Are specified by specifying their joint distribution. One can also choose the time points $t_1, \dots, t_n, \dots$ (where the process $X(t)$ is examined) in different ways.

An example of a Markov chain (MC), as the result of selecting one policy in the setup of Figure 1 (left). The policy displayed on the right-hand side is the optimal policy for this MDP, when starting in S_1 . The transition probabilities for the MC are shown in the matrix (right).

Source: (Seyr and Muskulus, 2019)

Calculations

- 1) Introducing two basic events

$\Theta = \{ \text{The transaction observes States } (0,0;i) \text{ and } (k,0;I,r) \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m_0, k \geq 1, 1 \leq r \leq m_2 \text{ only after arrived at the instant} \}$

And

$\Theta_c = \{\text{The transaction observes States } (k, l; I, j) \text{ for } k \geq 1, 1 \leq l \leq b, 1 \leq i \leq m_0, 1 \leq j \leq m_1 \text{ only after arrived at the instant}\}.$

It is easy to see that $\Theta \cup \Theta_c = \Omega$. Thus, the both events are complementary as per to the fact which tells that transaction can supervise all the states of the Markov process Q only after arrived at the instant. If the blockchain system stays uniform, it is simple to calculate the possibilities of both the events. Calculations of which as follows:

$$P\{\Theta\} = (0, \varphi)e = \varphi e$$

And

$$P\{\Theta_c\} = 1 - P\{\Theta\} = 1 - \varphi e.$$

After the application of law of total probability, we get

$$E[I] = P\{\Theta\}E[I | \Theta] + P\{\Theta_c\}E[I | \Theta_c] = \varphi e$$

$$E[\xi | (0, \varphi)] + (1 - \varphi e)E[\Gamma_s + \xi | (0, \varphi)] = E[\xi | (0, \varphi)] + (1 - \varphi e)E[\Gamma_s] = -(0, \varphi)H - 1e - (1 - \varphi e)\varpi T - 1e.$$

2)

If $(\theta_0 + \theta b)(D \otimes I) e < b \theta_0 [I \otimes (S_0 \alpha)] e$, it signifies that blockchain system has attained stability.

Therefore we write the following:-

$$N_1 = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} N_1(t), \quad N_2 = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} N_2(t),$$

Where $N_1(t)$ and $N_2(t)$ are some random transactions in a queueing waiting room and of transactions in the block at time $t \geq 0$, respectively.

a.

The average stationary number of transactions in the queueing waiting room

$$E[N_1] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \sum_{i=1}^m \pi_0 \sum_{r=1}^m \pi_2 \pi(I, r) k, 0 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \sum_{b=1}^1 \sum_{i=1}^m \pi_0 \sum_{j=1}^m \pi_1 \pi(I, j) k, l = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \sum_{b=1}^1$$

$$= 0 \pi_{k, l} e = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \pi_k e = \pi_1 R (I - R)^{-2} e.$$

It is to be noted that the above three vectors possess different sizes, for instance, the size of the first one is $m_0 \times m_2$ for $l=0$ and $m_0 \times m_1$ for $1 \leq l \leq b$, while the sizes of the second and third are $m_0 \times (m_2 + b m_1)$. Here we can use vector e .

b.

The average stationary number of transactions in the block

Let $h = (0, e, 2e, \dots, be)^T$. Then

$$E[N_2] = \sum_{l=0}^{b-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^{m_0} \sum_{j=1}^{m_1} \pi_{(i,j)k,l} = \sum_{l=0}^{b-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \pi_{k,l} \quad e = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \pi_k$$

$$h = [\pi_0 + \pi_1(I-R)^{-1}] h.$$

Human Computer Interaction

Human Computer Interaction system must be fast and one must be able to rely on it. Sign language recognition module is one such module. There are some cases where from the sign language module two or more features are derived. The SL system makes the process faster, but this cannot be taken into consideration if accuracy is compromised. This problem can be formulated by the task of planning the sequence of recognizer actions. The Partially Observable Markov Decision Processes (POMDPs) gives a mathematical framework that is adequate for such planning problems. A POMDP provides an explicitly formed module that contains the possibilities of observing numerous inputs.

Conclusion

Uncertainty is one of the primary factors which tend to worry the whole of mankind. In every field, there are certain uncertainties. Even in the personal life of every individual, certain uncertainties prevail. The primary and the most important reason for the uncertainty is, for the happening of an event various other factors need to act favorably for that event to take place. Now, to properly predict the uncertainties, proper understanding and reading of these various factors which are involved, is required. Scientists have worked hard over the years to come up with a formula such that it can read these involved factors and present a prediction regarding the most possible outcome. However, one cannot rely on these calculations because to perform the calculations records of the factors are taken into account, but it is not possible to ascertain the likely changes which may occur to these factors in the future because of the very fate of these factors is itself uncertain. This is the very reason why the Markov decision process experiences a major setback even though the calculations it provides have a high chance of being accurate. However, the Markov decision process is a key tool used by various institutions because it helps them to take important decisions regarding their finance by predicting the possible risks that they might have to face. Apart from predictions of risk, it also helps an investor to determine the possible market conditions which help them by giving them a brief idea of the fluctuations that may take place in the future. In the above paper, examples of calculations have been provided along with figures. The calculations are based on probabilities of the occurrence of two random events. Apart from that, detailed information and pictorial depiction of stochastic markov chain and stochastic matrix has been provided. Both of them serve as an important part of Markov decision making process. Therefore, this paper provides a detailed and informative insight of the mathematical tool.

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